

Synthetic and structural studies of heterocyclic N₄O₂ aldimine and its bivalent metal complexes

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Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes with 2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzene-1-carbalidene-2-aminobenzothiazole-3-carbalidene-2-amino-4-methylpyridine (HMBCABTCAMP) aldimine have been synthesized. The spectral data show metal-ligand bonding and stereochemistry in octahedral environment in all cases.

The present communication deals with the synthesis and characterization of complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} with the newly synthesized Schiff base 2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzene-1-carbalidene-2-aminobenzothiazole-3-carbalidene-2-amino-4-methylpyridine (HMBCABTCAMP) ligand (L, 1).

Results and discussion

All the chelates (Table 1) are coloured and insoluble in water and common organic solvents. Elemental analyses suggest their 1 : 2 metal · ligand stoichiometry. Molar conductance values of the complexes (less than 30 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) suggest their non-electrolytic nature.

Table 1. Physical data of the complexes*

Compd.**	Color	Decomp. temp.	μ _{eff} B.M.
[Co ^{II} L]	Orange	250	4.17
[Ni ^{II} L]	Red	300	3.21
[Zn ^{II} L]	Yellow	265	Dia.
[Cd ^{II} L]	Brown	245	Dia.

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

**L = HMBCABTCAMP (1).

IR spectra of the dicarbaldehyde reveal bands at 1695–1680 (C=O)¹, 2890–2880 (aldehydic CH)² and 3525 cm⁻¹ (phenolic OH)³.

The disappearance of the band at 3540–3525 cm⁻¹ (intramolecular hydrogen H-bonded phenolic OH) in the spectra of the metal complexes, indicates deprotonation of OH group and subsequent coordination of oxygen with the metal ion⁴. The strong band around 1625 cm⁻¹ (azomethine CH=N) and negative shift by 15–25 cm⁻¹ observed in all the metal chelates indicate participation of the azomethine nitrogen in chelate formation. New bands observed at 400 and 550 cm⁻¹ were for M–N and M–O⁵ respectively and confirm coordination through the deprotonated phenolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen, respectively.

¹H NMR spectra of the dicarbaldehyde show signals at δ 7.8 (m, ArH)^{6,7}, 2.4 (s, CH₃), 11.4 (phenolic H) and 10.2 (aldehydic H)⁸. ¹H NMR spectra of the ligand (1) show a singlet at δ 8.4 (CH=N)⁹. The broad signal observed at δ 11.2, characteristic of phenolic proton of the free ligand is absent in the metal complexes and this confirms the deprotonation of phenolic group of the ligand and formation of M–O bond.

Magnetic moment values of 4.17 and 3.21 B.M. for the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes provide evidence for their high-spin octahedral configuration. The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} chelate show three bands at 8045, 16540 and 21260 cm⁻¹ assignable to ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}, ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴A_{2g} and ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g} (P) transitions, respectively, confirming the octahedral geometry around Co^{II} ion¹⁰. The three bands observed in the Ni^{II} chelate at 10760, 17485 and 25735 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to the transition arising from ³A_{2g} ground state to ³T_{2g}, ³T_{1g} and ³T_{1g} (P) excited state, respectively, which supports octahedral geometry.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The solvents were purified and distilled prior to use.

2-Hydroxy-5-methylbenzene-1,3-dicarbaldehyde (HMBD) was prepared by reported procedure¹¹ (4 g, 28%), yellow, m.p. 130°.

Ligand (HMBCABTCAMP) :

The ligand **1** was prepared by refluxing an equimolar mixture of methanolic solution of the dicarbaldehyde (0.16 g, 1 mmol), 2-aminobenzothiazole (0.15 g, 1 mmol) and 2-amino-4-methylpyridine (0.11 g, 1 mmol). On cooling, the resulting yellowish red solid was washed with alcohol, crystallized from methanol and dried over anhyd. CaCl₂, (yield 0.25 g, 67%), yellowish red, m.p. 76°.

Metal complexes : A mixture of methanolic solution (15 ml) of the ligand (**1**; 0.77 g, 2 mmol) and methanolic solution (10 ml) of 1 mmol of the metal salt (0.25 g, Co(OAc)₂·4H₂O/0.25 g, Ni(OAc)₂·4H₂O/0.22 g, Zn(OAc)₂·2H₂O/0.18 g, CdCl₂) was refluxed. It was then cooled, concentrated at room temperature and the resulting solid was washed with alcohol, ether and dried in vacuum.

The compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses. C, H and N analyses were carried out on a Carlo-Erba-Micro 1106 analyzer. Sulfur was estimated as BaSO₄ by standard procedure¹². Metals were estimated by reported procedures¹³. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Jasco IR-Report-100 spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) on a Bruker AC (300 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and UV spectra on a Shimadzu UV 150-

150.02 spectrophotometer. Conductance was measured on a Toshniwal conductivity bridge using 10⁻³ M DMF solution. The magnetic susceptibility was determined at room temperature by Gouy's method.

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